

**Building the foundation for Norway's AI sovereignty
with Compute and Competence**

Funded by the Norwegian Research Council

Grant number: 322336

WORK PACKAGE FINAL REPORT

WP6: Business realization

Final Report - WP6 (Business realization)

- Document title: Final-REPORT-WP6
- DOI [10.5281/zenodo.20548785](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20548785)^a
- Creation date: 2026-03-27
- Document recorder name: Sabry Razick
- Document ID:34

- Deliverable ID: D6
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- Work-package(s):WP6
- Tasks included:
 - D6.1 Evaluate potential future services
 - D6.2 Define a business and sustainability model for operational phase
 - D6.3 Suggest Central data storage expansion and usage mod
 - D6.4 Acquire Data storage
 - D6.5 Investigate and recommend FAIR data stewardship
 - D6.6 Evaluate funding options for project sustainability
 - D6.7 Main procurement
 - D6.8 Handover to operations
- Completion Date: Plan completed 31-03-2026, implementation pending
- Time Spent: 12PM
- Approval:
 - Status:
 - Pending
 - Approved
 - Rejected
 - Approved by: [Name/title]
- Dissemination level
 - Private/Invited only
 - Work package
 - NAIC Project
 - Partners
 - Public

^a<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20548785>

Revision history

- [V10/04-06-2026/Sabry/Cosmetics security and privacy check,DOI]
- [V9/02-05-2026/Sabry/Set PM]
- [V8/09-04-2026/Abdulrahman/Aligned WP6 report with Sigma2 board-level process]
- [V7/05-04-206/Sabry/removed SIGMA2 board rejection narrative]
- [V6/31-03-206/Sabry,Maiken/Improved pain points]
- [V5/30-03-206/Ashen/technical implementations]
- [V4/30-03-206/Sabry/FAIR data solution]
- [V3/28-03-206/Sabry/Storage solution]
- [V2/27-03-206/Sabry/Include D6.1]
- [V1/27-03-206/Sabry/initial version]

Glossary of Terms

Term / Entity	Description
ARC	Advanced Resource Connector; the compute middleware that orchestrates jobs, interfacing with schedulers (like Slurm) and ensuring data is fully staged in local caches before a job executes.
CVMFS	CernVM File System; a dedicated architecture proposed for distributing read-only software caches globally, allowing VMs to mount software stacks without heavy local installations.
DataverseNO	A national, CoreTrustSeal-certified open-source repository proposed as a primary solution for FAIR data stewardship and long-term preservation.
dCache	(from. disk Cache) is a system for storing and retrieving huge amounts of data, that are distributed among a large number of heterogeneous server nodes,
DPA	Data Processing Agreement; a unified compliance framework for data handling that will replace the old NREC DBA under the new federated model.
EESSI	European Environment for Scientific Software Installations; used for software mounting to ensure the exact same set of modules and “look and feel” are available across all VMs, regardless of host infrastructure .
GPFS	IBM Storage Scale (formerly GPFS - General Parallel File System) is a high-performance, distributed clustered file system used for managing massive data sets, supporting simultaneous access from thousands of nodes.
IBM AFM	Active File Management; an edge-caching technology that creates synchronized, POSIX-compliant “warm caches” on local VMs and HPCs directly from the central repository.
iRODS	Proposed central link between the storage layer and user applications to enable policy-based data management and enhance metadata interoperability.
LMD	Lefdal Mine Datacenter; the physical location where Sigma2-owned hardware resources for the federated IaaS layer are hosted.
NAIC	Norwegian AI Cloud; a national project and platform providing the foundation for Norway’s AI sovereignty by offering local compute, multi-cloud provisioning, and AI competence.
NAIF	Norwegian AI Factory (also known as KI fabrikk); a collaborating entity
NIRD	The central storage system hosted by Sigma2, which acts as the NAIC Data Lake, storing both central project data and curated machine learning model caches.

Term / Entity	Description
NREC	Norwegian Research and Education Cloud; a federated Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS) layer used for providing private cloud resources across institutions like UiO and UiB.
NRIS	Norwegian Research Infrastructure Services; the national ecosystem where NAIC's baseline operations and Level 1 (L1) user support/Helpdesk are permanently embedded.
RCN	Research Council of Norway; the funding body for the NAIC project under grant number 322336.
REASON	ResEARch CommonS fOr Norway; a proposed generalist research infrastructure initiative that NAIC intends to integrate with for a comprehensive, policy-driven data lifecycle.
RFK	The allocation mechanism used by Sigma2 for managing quotas, cost-sharing, and tagging research facility allocations for NAIC users.
RSpace	An active data management platform proposed for integration to allow researchers to seamlessly transition active AI/ML data into long-term preservation.
Sigma2	The Service Owner of NAIC, operator of the NIRD storage system, and the primary governing body for national e-infrastructure and resource allocations.
Slurm	A workload manager and job scheduler used in NAIC clusters to dynamically allocate highly sought-after GPU and resources efficiently.
UCM	User Contribution Model; the cost-recovery and pricing framework used by Sigma2 to manage allocations for non-economic research (Categories A and B).
Waldur	The platform component integrated with the NAIC Orchestrator to handle national multi-cloud provisioning and resource management.
WP6	Work Package 6; the specific division of the NAIC project focused on Business Realization, transition to production, and the sustainability model.
Xet	A version management system utilizing block-level deduplication, proposed for efficiently managing and version-controlling massive ML models and datasets without redundant storage bloat.

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Executive Summary

This report outlines the transition of the Norwegian AI Cloud (NAIC) from its pilot phase into a permanent, sustainable national service designed to provide Norway with AI sovereignty through local compute and competence.

Pilot Phase and User Impact

The pilot period successfully gathered feedback by providing services at no cost to users, offset by NAIC grants that covered direct costs. Key user personas identified and supported include:

- Students (Future AI Pioneers): Master's and PhD candidates utilized GPU-optimized hardware (A100/L4) via Slurm clusters, saving between 5,880 NOK and 35,071 NOK per project compared to commercial cloud estimates.
- The Skills Accelerator: Provided massive, temporary scaling (e.g., 50+ VMs) for educational workshops like NLDL 2025 and Genomics.
- The Creative Technologist: Onboarded new disciplines, such as Arts and Humanities, by providing low-latency NREC resources for real-time AI applications

Technical Infrastructure

A robust, federated technical foundation was established to support long-term operations:

- Storage Solution: A cloud-ready federated storage system was proposed around the NIRD system, utilizing read-only caches on the edge to provide efficient data access to VMs.
- Orchestration: The NAIC Orchestrator (incorporating Waldur) was proposed as a permanent national service for multi-cloud provisioning on top of a federated IaaS layer.
- Data Management: Implemented a system where the orchestrator maps storage locations to user namespaces, ensuring secure data mounting within virtual environments.

Sustainability and Business Model

The NAIC Board approved a Business & Sustainability Model on October 13, 2025, to transition into a service operated by Sigma2/NRIS. The NAIC model has since been taken forward by Sigma2 as the foundation for a formal, national-level board investment case to establish a sovereign research cloud for Norway. This ensures that the WP6 outcomes are directly carried forward into a national implementation track under Sigma2 governance, rather than being treated as a standalone plan.

- Governance: Sigma2 serves as the Service Owner, with operations and user support (L1) embedded in the NRIS Helpdesk.
- Cost-Recovery: Pricing follows Sigma2's User Contribution Model (UCM) for non-economic research (Categories A and B) and market-price rules for economic activities/industry pilots (Category C).
- Synergy: Selected service functions, such as the Learning Hub and Outreach, will be co-funded by the Norwegian AI Factory (NAIF).

NAIC User personas and use case summary

We have summarized the use-cases and user customer personas/user personas of the NAIC users during the pilot period. As the aim of the pilot period was to get feed back on the services and plan the production phase, all service were provided at no cost fort he users. This provided though a NAIC grant which is equal to the direct cost for NAIC project when providing the service.

1. Student (Future AI pioneer)

- Role: Master’s / PhD Candidate (NTNU/UiB/UiO).
- Core Objective: Executing complex simulations and model training that exceed the capabilities of local hardware.
- Key Initiative: Utilizing ML optimized hardware on cloud with A100/L4 GPUs via SLURM queue manager for thesis-related computational experiments.

Table 1: Pain points student user

Pain Point	Solution
Limited access to high-tier local GPU resources (e.g., A100s) during peak academic periods.	Provided dedicated Slurm clusters with dynamic node allocation and NVIDIA L4/A100 GPU nodes.
The complexity of setting up a Slurm environment for dynamic node allocation all by self.	Enabled data preprocessing on cheaper VMs, recruiting high-value GPU VMs only when needed via a queue manager to reduce costs and bypass complex manual setups.
Budget constraints making commercial cloud instances (GCP/AZURE) prohibitively expensive for long-running research.	When local resources are saturated during peak periods, NAIC’s hybrid cloud setup provides cheaper commercial cloud options, significantly reducing waiting times.
Difficult to get the same environment on different cloud providers and geographically distant local clouds, and syncing images is not convenient.	NAIC uses cloud-init techniques to customize VMs from vanilla flavors, making reproducible VMs possible.Regardless of whether the VMs are spun up locally or on commercial clouds, they maintain the exact same look and feel thanks to EESSI software mounting, which ensures the same set of modules is available in all VMs.

- Infrastructure Value:
 - Commercial Cloud Estimate: Between 5,925 NOK and 16,918 NOK per project depending on the specific GPU architecture (L4 vs A100).
 - Resources Provided: Dedicated Slurm clusters with dynamic node allocation and NVIDIA L4/A100 GPU nodes. Student performs data preprocessing and workflow development on a cheap VM and the high value GPU VMs are recruited only when there is a need via queue manager. This makes it possible to share limited number of high value hardware with many users and to reduce the cost per user. In addition, as the high value nodes are powered up only when there is a direct need, this fits perfectly with NAIC sustainability goals.

Table 2: Example pilot projects

Project / Initiative	Resources Provided	Cost. (NOK)
NTNU Master Thesis	GCP Slurm Cluster (1x A100 GPU node + 2x CPU nodes)	16,918 NOK
Individual Student	GCP Slurm Cluster + 1x VM with 2x NVIDIA L4 GPUs	35,071 NOK
HVL Bachelor Project	1x VM with 1x NVIDIA L4 GPU	5,880 NOK

Project / Initiative	Resources Provided	Cost. (NOK)
UiB Master Project	1x VM with 1x NVIDIA L4 GPU	5,925 NOK

2. The skills accelerator (Educational Workshops)

- Role: Workshop Coordinator / Technical Lead (NLDL/Bioinformatics).
- Core Objective: Providing hands-on technical training to large groups of students or professionals simultaneously.
- Key Initiative: Organizing large-scale events like “NLDL 2025” or “Accelerating Genomics Workflows.”

Table 3: Pain points related to workshops

Pain Point	Solution
The need for massive, temporary horizontal scaling (e.g., 50+ VMs) that disappears after 24 hours.	Rapid provisioning of up to 50 Virtual Machines and specialized multi-GPU (4x L4) configurations to ensure short-term burst capacity at a much lower cost.
Requirement for uniform environments across all participants to avoid support issues.	Instructors can optimize a single VM environment and then clone it to ensure perfectly uniform environments for all participants.
High cost of provisioning dozens of GPU-enabled instances on commercial clouds for a single day.	Utilizing shared mounted storage any data modifications the instructor makes are propagated live, updating all participant VMs simultaneously.

Table 4: Example pilot projects

Project / Initiative	Resources Provided	Cost. (NOK)
NLDL 2025 Workshop	50 Virtual Machines for 1 day	3,213 NOK
Bioinformatics Workshop	10x GCP VMs with 4x NVIDIA L4 GPUs each	830 NOK

3. The Creative Technologist-new discipline on boarding (Arts & Humanities)

- Role: Lead Developer / Researcher (Musicology/IFI).
- Core Objective: Integrating AI into real-time creative processes, such as live music performance or robotic interaction.
- Key Initiative: dB: A Web-based Drummer Bot, utilizing machine learning for finger-tapping interaction.

Table 5: Pain points related AI creativity users

Pain Point	Solution
The need for low-latency processing to ensure real-time response to human input.	Provided hosted instances on the NREC (Norwegian Research and Education Cloud) optimized for web-service delivery and low-latency interaction.
Hosting a web-based service accessible to performers while maintaining a secure backend.	Provided 10,000 NOK worth of local infrastructure to support the project’s computational needs.

Pain Point	Solution
Navigating public-sector cloud restrictions (NREC) while developing non-traditional AI applications.	Provided 50 hours of consultation to deliver an optimal configuration for a production-ready web service, helping researchers navigate technical hurdles.

- Infrastructure Value:
 - Cost estimate: 10,000 NOK cloud credit, 50 hours (around 40,000 NOK) of consultation and configuration support
 - Resources Provided: Hosted instances on the NREC (Norwegian Research and Education Cloud) optimized for web-service delivery and low-latency interaction.

Table 6: Example pilot projects

Project / Initiative	Resources Provided	Cost. (NOK)
Music Project (IFI)	Private Cloud Resources (NREC)	10,000 NOK cloud credit on Local Cloud

Strategic Value Proposition

- Sovereignty: Ensures the legal and physical entity hosting the data is local, satisfying national security concerns.
- Flexibility: Allows for custom network architecture and modifications to usual workflows that rigid public clouds do not support.
- Cost Efficiency: Allows for dynamic resource allocation so infrastructure does not sit idle, providing a transparent cost structure for startups.
- Collaboration: Creates secure “sandbox” environments where industry and education can collaborate without violating industrial secrecy.
- Cut through red tape: The pilot projects for NAIC are a good example for quick and non bureaucracy way of providing access.

NAIC - Norwegian AI Cloud

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🔗 Research Highlight: Using NAIC Resources for Energy Systems Research

Hans Kristian Ovanger has been working on reinforcement learning ...more

Hans O. • 3rd+

Research Engineer | RL/Reasoning

7mo • 🌐

Earlier this summer I had the opportunity to present my research at the 46th IAEE International Conference in Paris.

My talk focused on safe and efficient heat pump control using Masked Proximal Policy Optimization (Masked PPO).

(This just means that we built a learning robot that only makes safe choices while keeping people comfortable and saving energy.)

A big thanks to [Anne F. Neumann](#), and to [NAIC - Norwegian AI Cloud](#) for grant support and GPU resources on VMs that made this work possible.

Figure 1: LinkedIn post - Energy system research

Fabrizio Palumbo • Following
Associate Professor, OsloMet
6mo • 🔒

The GAIJ project is entering its final month!
At OsloMet and NMBU, the AIJRC group has explored how graph-augmented AI can support investigative journalism and transparency in financial reporting. Running LLMs is always computationally demanding, which is costly, especially for small-scale research projects. We are thankful to NAIC (Norwegian Artificial Intelligence Cloud) for providing us with the infrastructure to run our simulations and helping us set up our models. They helped the team bring GAIJ to life.
[#AI](#) [#Research](#) [#Journalism](#) [#NAIC](#) [#GAIJ](#)

Graph-bound AI Journalism in Financial Fraud (GAIJ)

Norwegian
University of
Life Sciences

Norwegian AI Cloud

Figure 2: LinkedIn post GAIJ project

Cloud ready federated storage solution

NAIC storage solution was planned around the NIRD system hosted by SIGMA2. The plan includes paying a rent for using the NIRD storage or investing in NIRD expansion, that would satisfy NAIC storage needs.

Storage needs

1. A central storage to maintain a curated cache of models which could be accessed from different HPC systems as well as from cloud VMs
2. A central data storage which could be accessed from different HPC systems as well as from cloud VMs

Main issues to be addressed

1. Where and how to host the central data storage
2. How the user name space will be managed
3. How the cache is maintained

Data access management in VMs

When the username space management system is in place, the orchestrator would have a mapping to storage locations the currently logged-in user should have access to. During provisioning, a read-only cache of the paths selected by the user would be placed inside the VM. The intention is to allow green data at first. For higher privacy levels, we need to develop an encryption mechanism, before publishing this feature. The data ownership inside the VMs is owned by VM users, not the original owner. The user who creates the VM is responsible to make sure that the VM is not distributed to third parties, with private data mounted. For example, a course organizer could create a set of VMs for students with data needed for the course mounted. The course organizer in this case is responsible for providing only the intended data.

Figure 3: NAIC storage solution with read-only caches on the edge

Inside the VM the mounts will be readable for VM user. Which means actual ownership information will not be propagated. If the requested data is large, this may take longer time to cache. To stop wasting VM resources, the VM would be provisioned only when the data is ready. The progress of the process would be notified to the user. A VM with large amount of data would take long time to be available. The Meta-data manager provides awareness about warm data to the data manager. Therefore, already cached data would be updated only if there is a change in checksum. In the case that a course organizer creates VMs with data they have access to, the course students

would have read-only access to those data. The responsibility to control which data should the students have access is transferred to the course organizer in this case.

Figure 4: NAIC storage proposed solution

Technology evaluation details

Data access management in VMs

The NAIC hybrid cloud strategy requires a robust, distributed data access system that bridges the gap between central storage, edge VMs, and high-performance computing (HPC) clusters (e.g., Fox, Saga). To address these requirements, the project evaluated and successfully tested a multi-tiered architecture that strictly separates user data caching, software provisioning, and compute lifecycle management.

Central Storage and The Global Namespace

At the core of the architecture is the NAIC central storage facility, mapped to the existing NIRD infrastructure, which utilizes the IBM Elastic Storage System (ESS) hardware running the IBM Storage Scale (formerly GPFS) file system. A primary challenge in distributed access is maintaining a unified, secure global namespace across diverse infrastructure (HPCs, NREC OpenStack instances, and commercial clouds).

To solve this, the architecture maps storage endpoints to national and federated identity providers, such as IDporten, Feide, Puhuri, and EduCloud. This ensures that when a VM or HPC job is provisioned, the user’s namespace is securely and automatically transferred, granting them identical access rights whether they are logging into Saga or an NREC VM.

Tiered Storage and Orchestration: dCache, IBM AFM, and ARC

Rather than relying on a single storage technology to handle all workloads, the NAIC architecture relies on a tiered ecosystem using evaluated NT1 technologies alongside IBM’s native capabilities. These tools are not competing, but rather form a unified pipeline for data ingestion, edge caching, and compute orchestration:

1. The Data Lake and Ingestion Tier (dCache): For massive-scale data ingestion and long-term storage, the architecture leverages dCache. As evaluated in the NT1 investigations, dCache excels at high-throughput ingestion from multiple external sources (lab equipment, sensors) and manages data consistently across geographic locations. It acts as the foundational, highly scalable data repository.
2. The High-Performance Edge Cache (IBM AFM): Data sitting in a central lake is inherently too slow for direct, active compute processing. To bridge this gap, the project successfully tested IBM Active File Management (AFM). AFM creates “warm,” POSIX-compliant caches directly

on NREC VMs and local HPCs. It actively pulls and synchronizes the necessary active datasets from the central NIRD/dCache repositories to the compute edge, ensuring lightning-fast local I/O for running jobs.

3. The Compute Orchestrator (ARC): Tying the storage and compute together is the Advanced Resource Connector (ARC). ARC serves as the compute middleware interfacing with job schedulers like Slurm. When a user submits an AI/ML job, ARC checks where the data resides. It coordinates with the storage tier to ensure data is staged into the local IBM AFM cache, and crucially, ensures Slurm only executes the compute job *after* the data is fully available locally.

Software Provisioning via CVMFS

While IBM AFM handles dynamic user data, the investigation determined that software environments and container images require a different approach to avoid storage bloat.

For software provisioning, the project proposes leveraging the CernVM File System (CVMFS). By deploying a dedicated CVMFS architecture, read-only software caches can be distributed globally. This allows VMs and HPC nodes to instantly mount complex software stacks and execution environments over the network, completely bypassing the need for heavy, localized software installations.

Compute Lifecycle Management

To encourage efficient resource usage, NAIC VMs have a maximum uptime of 48 hours. However, to support longer pipelines, the project designed a snapshot-based persistence model. When a VM hits its timeout, OpenStack is configured to snapshot the VM rather than delete it. These snapshots can then be securely transferred and spun back up across different NREC instances (e.g., moving from UiO to UiB) without losing the cached state.

Figure 5: Technology assesment for NAIC cloud ready storage solution

Real-World Application: Multi-Site Workshop Data Sharing

The efficacy of this architecture is highlighted by a validated multi-site workshop use case. In scenarios where an instructor must provide 500GB of shared data to 20 VMs distributed across both UiO and UiB NREC instances, localized storage replication is cost-prohibitive and difficult to keep synchronized. Under the proposed architecture:

1. The 500GB dataset resides on the central NIRD storage.
 2. IBM AFM maintains a synchronized “warm cache” at both the UiO and UiB edge sites.
 3. The individual participant VMs mount this local, site-specific cache via NFS.
 4. If the instructor modifies the central data, AFM immediately propagates the changes to both edge caches, updating all 20 VMs simultaneously.
- This architecture ensures high performance, minimal storage redundancy, and a seamless experience for the end user.

Figure 6: Use-case example for NAIC cloud ready storage solution

Proposed Next Steps: Expanding the NAIC Data Architecture

Building upon the successful evaluation of the tiered storage and orchestration architecture (dCache, IBM AFM, and ARC), the project proposes the following next steps to transition from a POC infrastructure into a fully featured AI/ML platform.

1. Unified Central NAIC Data Lake with Universal Cache Management

The immediate next step is to operationalize the Central NAIC Data Lake on the NIRD infrastructure. This data lake will serve as the single source of truth for all project data.

To ensure performance and accessibility, the previously validated IBM AFM cache management system will be deployed across all edge endpoints. This guarantees that the central data lake is seamlessly and securely accessible from:

- Virtual Machines (NREC instances across UiO, UiB,UiA etc.)
- Local and National HPC systems (Fox, Saga, Betzy)
- User devices and workstations
- Commercial cloud environments

By centralizing the data and distributing the caches, users will experience local I/O performance across all platforms without the overhead of manual data staging or redundant storage.

As the initial set of data, the data from the MLOPS/demonstrators could be made available as data for initial users as well as examples for other data depositors (described in details under WP7).

2. Curated Machine Learning Model Hub (Xet-based Versioning)

As NAIC supports increasingly complex AI/ML workloads, managing large model weights (e.g., foundation models, fine-tuned checkpoints) becomes a critical storage challenge. We propose establishing a centrally located, curated list of machine learning models.

To manage the massive file sizes associated with these models, this hub will be built using a Xet-based version management system (the underlying storage architecture utilized by platforms like Hugging Face).

- **Efficient Versioning:** Xet-based storage allows for block-level deduplication, meaning users can version-control massive model checkpoints without duplicating the entire file size for minor changes.
- **Integration with Caching:** Placed on top of our IBM AFM and dCache architecture, the Xet system will allow users to rapidly pull specific versions of a model directly into their local compute cache, ensuring reproducibility for AI experiments.

3. Versioned Repository for Raw and Processed Data

The same Xet-based architecture proposed for the model hub will be extended to manage training datasets. In ML workflows, tracking the exact state of data used for training is as important as tracking the code.

We propose a structured setup for:

- **Raw Data:** Immutable central storage for original datasets, securely ingested and preserved.
- **Processed Data:** A version-controlled environment where researchers can branch, modify, and process data for specific experiments. Utilizing Xet-based versioning ensures that data pipelines are fully reproducible, and researchers can instantly mount specific versions of processed datasets to their HPC jobs or VMs via the AFM cache.

4. FAIR Data Stewardship and Management: The DataverseNO and REASON Proposal

To ensure that the massive amounts of data generated, processed, and stored within the NAIC hybrid cloud adhere to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles, the project investigated the integration of established national data repositories.

While not fully implemented during the pilot phase, the project proposes adopting DataverseNO(<https://dataverse.no/>) as a primary solution for FAIR data stewardship. DataverseNO is a national, CoreTrustSeal-certified repository operated at UiT in collaboration with partner institutions. It is built upon the globally adopted, community-driven Dataverse open-source application.

This proposal integrates NAIC's storage strategy with the broader REASON (ResEARCh CommonS fOR Norway) initiative. REASON is a proposed generalist research infrastructure designed to implement the essential elements of the Global Open Research Commons (GORC) model published by the Research Data Alliance (RDA).

By connecting the NAIC storage architecture with the REASON framework, the project can establish a comprehensive, policy-driven data lifecycle:

- **Policy-Based Data Management:** The architecture proposes implementing iRODS as the central link between the underlying storage layer (e.g., NIRD, IBM AFM caches) and user applications. This will significantly enhance Research Object and metadata interoperability and governance.

- Active Data Integration: The solution will connect with active data management platforms like RSpace, allowing researchers to seamlessly move data from active AI/ML processing into long-term preservation.
- AI and ML Innovations: The proposed collaboration directly targets joint development in “AI and ML Innovations for Advanced Research Services” and “Research Object Transformation, Curation, Provability”.

By adopting this DataverseNO/REASON framework, NAIC will bridge the gap between high-performance compute edge caching and long-term FAIR data stewardship, providing users with a secure, citable, and reproducible pathway for their AI datasets and models.

Proposed sustainability plan

The sustainability plan *D6.2: Business & Sustainability Model for the NAIC Operational Phase* detailed in [Appendix 1](#) was unanimously approved by the NAIC board on 13-10-2025 as the preferred sustainability direction. This model has subsequently been taken forward and operationalized by Sigma2 as part of a formal, board-level investment case for national cloud infrastructure (SIGMA2 internal documents Sak 12-26: Investering i Sky e-infrastruktur and Sak 40-26: Investments in Cloud infrastructure), where it forms a core foundation for the proposed national implementation.

As the infrastructure serves a broader national role beyond NAIC, the implementation is handled through this extended governance and investment process, which requires additional evaluation time at the Sigma2 board level. As a result, the final procurement utilizing NAIC funds has been temporarily postponed, and the project has entered a no-cost hibernation phase pending final decision.

Current Status and Deviations

The transition from pilot to production has been delayed due to the timing of the final procurement decision. The WP6 sustainability model and infrastructure direction have not been handled as a standalone deliverable, but have been fully integrated into a broader Sigma2 board-level investment case for national cloud infrastructure. In this context, the recommended path for cloud procurement (establishment of an LMD region as part of the NREC federation) is currently in the final stages of board-level decision-making. Given the national scope and long-term implications of this infrastructure, the process requires staged governance and evaluation. As a result, the project has entered a no-cost hibernation phase while awaiting final board approval and procurement execution. A change notice was submitted to the Research Council requesting this hibernation until Sigma2's final procurement is in place. The change notice is included with the WP1 (Project governance and management reporting). The work delivered under WP6 therefore represents a direct foundation for a national infrastructure investment process, rather than a standalone plan awaiting approval.

As the RCN-funded active period formally concluded on March 31, 2026, the project can no longer cover expenses. Consequently, effective April 1st, all NAIC-funded staff activities have been halted until the final procurement and sustainability plan are fully operationalized. To mitigate the severe risk of losing highly specialized personnel and project momentum during this delay, a strategic continuity measure was enacted by transitioning key NAIC staff and work scopes to the newly established National AI Factory (KI-fabrikken).

Appendix-1

D6.2: Business & Sustainability Model for the NAIC Operational Phase

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1. Executive Summary

NAIC will transition its proven pilots (orchestrator, support, learning hub, monitoring, and outreach) into steady-state services operated with Sigma2/NRIS and embedded in the national e-infrastructure ecosystem. The target operating model places NAIC Orchestrator (with Waldur) as a permanent national service on top of a federated IaaS layer (NREC + Sigma2), with user support embedded in NRIS Helpdesk. Pricing and cost-recovery follow Sigma2's User Contribution Model (UCM) for research allocations and market-price rules for economic activity. Staffing of selected NAIC service functions will be co-funded by the Norwegian AI Factory (NAIF) (mainly user enablement and outreach), with deliverables aligned to NAIF work plans and deliverables. All underlying IT and infrastructure services (compute, storage, networking, identity/AAI, observability, backups, and lifecycle management) will be operated and maintained by the National Cloud service under Sigma2/NRIS operational processes.

Note on NREC Federation agreement: Negotiations and formalization are in progress. We present the NREC federation as the preferred and most probable operational plan, while avoiding any binding commitments on Sigma2's behalf until the agreement is signed.

2. Governance & Roles

2.1 Oversight and reporting

- Project/Service oversight will follow the consortium governance: a Board/Steering function approves annual work plans and the formal scientific/financial reporting to RCN; Project Lead reports to the Board and is the contact point to RCN. This aligns with the Konsortieavtale's governance and reporting clauses.
- Operational steering for platform and services will align with the NREC/NRIS steering structures when the NREC federation agreement is concluded. Until then, NAIC continues under existing Sigma2/NRIS governance for national services.

2.2 Roles summary

- Service Owner: Sigma2 (within NRIS service portfolio).
- Operations:
 - Service layer (NAIC Orchestrator + Waldur, SP/Kubernetes integrations): Sigma2/NRIS teams, with NAIC design authority for orchestrator policy packs.
 - IaaS layer: NREC platform teams at UiO/UiB (+ NTNU where applicable) and Sigma2-owned resources at LMD. Ownership remains per-site, per the agreement.
- User Support: Embedded in NRIS Helpdesk (L1), with Sigma2 and NREC platform (L2, L3).
- Data Processing & Compliance: Common DPA framework under the federated model (new DPA replaces old NREC DBA when NREC federation is concluded).

3. Service Scope (What We Run Nationally)

3.1 Permanent services

- NAIC Orchestrator (with Waldur): national, policy-driven multi-cloud provisioning on top of NREC/Sigma2 IaaS; integrates with RfK allocation tagging and quota sync.
 - NAIC User Support: single front door via NRIS Helpdesk.
 - Learning Hub: curated training pathways, aligned with NRIS training calendar.
 - Resource Monitor: common dashboards for capacity, usage, and service health.
 - Outreach & Communications: www.naic.no¹, LinkedIn, NORA newsletter.
- All five components have completed POC and will be sustained in operations.

¹<http://www.naic.no>

3.2 Underlying IaaS (federated plan) Preferred plan is the NREC Federation with a Sigma2-owned region at LMD, plus UiO/UiB (and NTNU where applicable). Each site retains ownership and legal responsibility for its hardware and services; Sigma2 owns Sigma2-purchased equipment at LMD. *Status:* agreement work in progress.

4. Ownership, IP, and Use of Infrastructure [1]

- Hardware ownership: Each site retains ownership for on-site equipment purchased on their budget; Sigma2 retains ownership for equipment it purchases. Sites make resources available to NAIC users per the resource-sharing key; local OPEX (power, footprint) is carried in-kind by the owner.
- Software/IP: Software developed in the project should be Open Source; contributing partners retain access to contributed code even if they later exit. *This matches the NAIC Konsortieavtale Annex statements.*

5. User Access & Allocation Policy

We harmonize with Sigma2 allocations and the consortium framework:

- Primary beneficiaries: publicly funded research and education institutions (non-economic activities).
- Allocation: Sigma2 allocates to “Sigma2 users” via RFK in parity with other national facilities; university-owned capacity may also be allocated via their mechanisms—convergence is targeted but not guaranteed (the agreement permits divergence).
- Non-economic vs. economic use: We separate these activities to prevent cross-subsidization. Economic use (e.g., commissioned research or services to external parties) will be offered on market terms and only within current Sigma2 policy. We will monitor and plan such usage and include it in our annual reporting to RCN [1].

6. Pricing & Cost-Recovery

6.1 Principles

- Non-economic research: follows Sigma2’s UCM via RFK cost-sharing for allocations where applicable.
- Economic activity: delivered on market terms in line with current Sigma2 policy and pricing guidelines. Where needed, pricing will follow Sigma2’s approved methodology. Compliance is handled through standard financial reporting; any change in scope or volume will be brought to the board as a separate decision.

6.2 Categories (mapped to UCM & agreement)

- Category A: Research baseline: centrally funded quotas for national higher-education/research via RFK (non-economic).
- Category B: Extended research demand: cost-recovery at RFK-compatible unit rates (non-economic).
- Category C: Projects & industry pilots: Provided on market terms with full cost-recovery (including any GPU premiums and dedicated support), delivered within current Sigma2 policy. Any expansion of scope or volume will be brought to the board as a separate decision.

7. Operations Model

- Run: Service layer by Sigma2/NRIS; IaaS by NREC sites + Sigma2 LMD. Responsibility stays with the site owner per the agreement.
- Support: L1 NRIS Helpdesk; L2 Sigma2 federation/service team; L3 NREC infrastructure teams.
- Change & Release: Harmonized maintenance windows, CI/CD for orchestrator, transparent comms via Helpdesk and status pages.
- Compliance: New common DPA enacted with the federation; data classification and retention align with NRIS policy.
- SLA indicators: Availability, fulfilment times, issue resolution SLAs; quarterly KPI reviews.

8. Sustainability Plan

- People: Combined Sigma2/NRIS service staff and NREC site teams (UiO/UiB/NTNU) with clear role separation; right-sized FTEs for service layer and platform. (The in-progress NREC agreement text anticipates dedicated FTEs and funding commitments for platform and service layer.)
- OPEX funding:
 - Baseline operations for A/B via UCM/RFK cost-sharing.
 - Premium services, dedicated support, and industry pilots via market-price Category C.
- Post-RCN cost recovery (as already recorded in the agreement annex): EU/national programmes, Sigma2’s current research infrastructure funding module, paid advanced user support, research-grant user payments, and sales to non-academic users up to the 20% capacity cap.

9. Monitoring, Reporting, and Audit Readiness

- Capacity accounting: We pre-estimate, track, and annually report the economic-use share to RCN
 - evidence includes capacity, time accounting, and separate cost/income ledgers.
- Financials: Consortium payment flows and rights to withhold payment for defaulting partners follow the agreement.
- Quality: Ticketing metrics, availability reports, and post-mortems delivered via NRIS Helpdesk and NAIC dashboards.

10. Risk and Compliance

- Policy constraint on economic use: If demand exceeds the current Sigma2 policy, we will return to the board with options. Until then, we operate within the existing constraint.
- Agreement dependency risk (NREC federation): Tracked as a programme risk
 - interim operations continue under current Sigma2/NRIS governance
 - No binding promises are made on behalf of Sigma2 until signature.
- Operational risks: Capacity bottlenecks, API drift, talent constraints—mitigated by procurement planning, contract test suites, and staffing plan.

11. Transition of Pilots into Operations

All POC components are scheduled for handover into operations and are included in the sustainability plan:

- Multi-cloud provisioning (NAIC Orchestrator + Waldur): permanent national service under Sigma2/NRIS.
- NAIC User Support: embedded in NRIS Helpdesk.
- Learning Hub: maintained with NRIS training calendar (co-funded by NAIF).
- Resource Monitor: national dashboards integrated with NRIS observability.
- Outreach: www.naic.no², LinkedIn, NORA newsletter (co-funded by NAIF).

Ownership and cost handling follow the per-site model and market-price rules for economic activity, as specified in the agreement annexes.

12. Dependencies and Next Steps

1. Finalize NREC Federation agreement (in progress) with governance, DPA, RFK integration, and site responsibilities as outlined in the draft collaboration text.
2. Publish pricing handbook detailing Category A/B/C mapping to UCM and market-price methodology for Category C (ESA §§25–26 basis where applicable)[1].
3. Operationalize reporting for economic-use share and financial separation to support annual RCN reporting and audits.

Reference

[1] Konsortieavtale Norwegian Artificial Intelligence Cloud

²<http://www.naic.no>